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Annatasi: Physical education development Gradually , historically process during people more active and mobile marriage style take went tribe members this that he repeated attention focus must or another physical actions , physical strength showed that it is stronger and more durable and more efficient was It's people physical exercises (movements repetition) event conscious respectively to understand take came

Keywords: modeling, done increase criteria, health to keep improvement, modes, environment.

Physical education and of sports appear to be and formation about this of direction essence and appear to be reasons in society physical education Physical education appear to be for years go is worn humanity society of history initial era Elements physical education primitive in society to the body came (NI Ponomarev, 1970). People own to food have they were, ov they did they built a house and this natural, necessary activity in the process their physical abilities - strength, endurance, speed - by themselves improved.

Gradually , historically process during people more active and mobile marriage style take went tribe members this that he repeated attention focus must or another physical actions , physical strength showed that it is stronger and more durable and more efficient was It's people physical exercises (movements repetition) event conscious respectively to understand take came Physical education to the basis has become physical exercises event was Physical exercises effect understand and imitate started his work in the activity to him necessary has been actions (movement). real work from the process except , for example , of an animal to the image spear shoot Labor actions real work from processes outside apply started immediately they are physical to exercises turned . Labor activities physical to exercises rotate their effect scope significant level expanded person per head and the first in turn comprehensively physical improvement point of view in terms of From this except , evolutionary development in the process known to be physical education in training significant level good to the effect man exercise do it when he started is achieved childhood , and in adults not , that is , to life and to life while preparing in advance work process to quality was considered

Marked of the object (of the event) eng important aspects , features or signs on and to express

Physical the main theory of education1 concepts the following includes: 1) " physical education ";

- 2) " physical preparation ";
- 3) " physical development ";
- 4) "physical perfection ";
- 5) "sport".

Physical education. It's to himself typical education is the type. His content - to actions teaching, physical adjectives education, special physical education knowledge appropriation and physical education to training conscious the need formation

Movement training own content as physical to the content have

Education is a person by own actions of management reasonable methods regularly respectively work output, that's it with in life necessary movement skills basis take over and belongs to knowledge.

Life or for sports important the actions of the appropriation through students their own physical qualities reasonable and complete manifestation to do ability eg a will be With that Together, they are body movements free movement process they learn

Appropriation level according to, action action technique two in form - movement skills in the form of done increase possible and skill in the form of. That's why for physical education learning in practice the phrase " movements ". instead of they are most of the time they use" motor skills the term " formation ".

Physical qualities development physical education one different level important aspect is considered Strength, speed, endurance, flexibility and quickness physical of virtues progressive development purposeful manage natural to complexes effect does of the organism properties and that's it with quantitative and determines his in functionality quality changes.

All physical qualities is innate, that is given development and improvement need has been natural desire in the form of to the individual and natural development process when special organize done takes, that is. Pedagogical to the feature have if not " development " but " physical qualities " to educate ". more correct.

Physical education in the process wide comprehensive physical education and sports knowledge, sociological, hygienic, medical and methodical content. Knowledge physical exercises process more meaningful and therefore for more efficient does

So so, physical education certain eating and education problems solution to do process pedagogical of the process all features have has been tasks. Physical education to himself typical feature it is the ability to move and skills systematic respectively to form and physical purposeful development provides of a person total his physical opportunities solution doer level defines qualities.

Physical education " Physical the term " education ". physical education practical direction emphasizes the work or another activity for. General physical features there is training and special.

General physical preparation degree to increase directed physical development, wide tool readiness different at events to success reach for necessary conditions as.

Special physical training - specialized certain in action to success help giving process (kind of profession , sport and others) to human ability to move special requirements puts Physical of preparation result physical preparation is purposeful of activity efficiency contribution adding formed tool skills and in their abilities achieved the results reflection makes (this purposeful of activity efficiency to increase focused).

Physical development. This is formation, formation is a process and from him next changes of a person whole life during happen will be his of the body morphofunctional features and based on their physical qualities and abilities.

Physical development three in the group changes with is described indicators.

1. Physical indicators (body length, body weight, posture, body separately parts volumes and forms of fatty compounds quantity and others), they the first in line biological is characterized **Of the person forms or morphology.**

2. Morphology reflection bringer health indicators (criteria). Physiological in systems makes sense and functional changes a person body Man health for solution doer important have heart-blood vein, breath get bodies to work effect does and central nerve system, food digestion to do and release organs nia, thermoregulation mechanisms and others

3. Physical of adjectives development indicators (power, speed abilities, endurance and others). Until about 25 years of age (formation and growth period) many morphological indicators increases dimensions and bodily functions will improve. Then up to 45-50 years during physical development known level stabilized it seems Later, we are old sain, of the body functional activity little by little weakens and gets worse

Body length, muscle mass and others decrease can

Life during this of indicators change process as physical of development nature a lot reasons depends and series laws with is determined. Successful manage physical development only this patterns known if and they are in construction account is taken physical education process.

Physical development known level laws with is determined Heredity, that is physical the situation supportive or on the contrary, prevention receiver factors as attention taken need human improvement. Heredity, in particular of a person possibilities and in sports success prophecy in doing attention get need

Physical development the process is also young gradation (of the earth weight power) to the law obeys. Human physical development to the process only basically control to do for interference possible different young periods a person of the body features and opportunities account received without: formation and growth during his forms and of functions the most high development during, aging during Physical development process unity to the law obeys organism and the environment and therefore for significant level of a person to live conditions depend First in line to live conditions social conditions enters Live conditions, work, education and material help significant level effect does of a person physical status and of the body forms and of functions development and to change determines Geographical the environment is also physical to development known effect shows.

Physical development manage for big important have Physical education process physical of exercises biological to the law and of the organism forms and of functions unit to the law have

This laws in choosing initial each is a point sure in case physical education tools and methods.

Physical exercises choose and their size determination downloads, exercises ability to the law according to count possible attraction done in the body necessary adaptive changes for. This is the body one whole as work account takes That's why for exercises and loads in choosing, mainly selective influence, their of influence all aspects sure imagination to do need

Physical perfection It is historical defined of my body is ideal of a person physical development and physical preparation;

life requirements the most suitable will come.

Ours of our time physically perfect of the person the most important to himself typical indicators:

1) good health to a person chance give, that's it including , adapts and life , work , marriage uncomfortable conditions ;

2) high common physical indicators, I allow I will give important special to indicators to achieve the goal did

3) proportional developed physics, right to stand up , it is known anomalies and of disparities absence ;

4) comprehensive and perfect developed physical virtues; of a person one bilaterally development an exception to do

5) main of vitality rational technique take over actions are also new actions quickly learning ability negative actions ;

6) physical education, that is . special ownership knowledge and from your body efficient use ability and in life , at work , in sports physical abilities .

Society of development present stage physical of maturity main criteria the norm and are requirements state programs combined standards with joint sports classification .

Sports. Real competitiveness represents activity, to him separately training as well as interpersonal relationships and to him typical has been norms

Sports to himself typical feature is this to himself typical shape has been competition activity

Competitors mutually relationships sure in order putting , actions composition (of the projectile weight , opponent , distance and others) combine , they for conditions based on of a person opportunities identification , comparison and comparison enable giving competitions , defined according to done increase and achievements evaluation methods rules .

Competition events special preparatory sports training sports training in the form of done is increased.

XXI century in their heads education in philosophy important changes in education humanity direction increase physical education issues updated : what for , who and how teaching and educate ?

Received to questions answer looking for one series of scientists to his thoughts Based on the physical education pedagogical models systematized.

Human to live methods and environment to himself typical features and others are also physical culture of appearances appear to be and of diversity essence analysis to do and others to us possibility gave Physical education in the field pedagogical of models real collection their anthropological and ontological structural parts , that is mutually depends and mutually depends has been two or of the vector this combination with is determined to the conclusion arrival : "body-soul " and " nature-culture ". physical education four pedagogical model determination for base

Health to keep within the adaptive model physical education purpose health improve the normal physical condition of students development and common physical preparation reach, their natural and social life conditions adaptation for necessary individual morphofunctional and motor base is to create. This in the model of the environment role not only physical exercises, maybe natural factors are also wide apply through of the teacher of the student physical -motor potential , its individual characteristics account received without adaptive training effect with depend sun , air , water).

in the east healthy and flexible physical education development traditions of Ayurvedic teachings and of treatment prophylactic methods principles come turns out , their philosophical

basis is cosmocentrism . In the west natural centrism and natural compliance ideas Aristotle , Democritus , Plato , later names with connected . Rousseau. However, in pedagogy to nature compatibility principle the founder Yes. A. Komensky is " school's sure order from nature get it is necessary," he said.

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